

1 **The role of climate change in the extinction of the last wild equids of Europe: palaeoecology of**
2 ***Equus ferus* and *Equus hydruntinus* during the Last Glacial Period**

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13
14 **Abstract**

15 The last European wild equids —*Equus ferus* and *Equus hydruntinus*— were among the
16 large mammals (or megafauna) that became extinct during the Late Quaternary Extinction Event
17 disappearing from Europe during the Holocene. The role that the combined action of the major
18 climatic changes of the Pleistocene/Holocene Transition and the human activities played in their
19 extinction is not fully understood. The reduction of steppe-like biomes in Europe following the
20 increase of mean global temperatures during the Holocene is usually regarded as the main event that
21 triggered their disappearance, as both equids display typical morphological adaptations for open
22 grasslands and grass eating. However, *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* are found, often even co-
23 occurring, in both warm and cold phases of the Late Pleistocene. Thus, the investigation of their
24 niche occupation can help decipher whether their ecology and specialised dietary adaptations were
25 the main reason of their decline following the early Holocene global warming. ~~A rich collection of~~
26 ~~*E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* fossil material has been unearthed from the Late Pleistocene cave of La~~

27 ~~Carihuela (Granada, Iberian Peninsula), making this locality an optimal laboratory to investigate~~
28 ~~their palaeoecology.~~ Here we investigate the feeding strategies of the two equids by studying their
29 long- and short-term dietary adaptations ~~by examining~~through examination of their patterns of
30 dental wear. As expected, dental mesowear points to a highly abrasive diet concordant with a
31 grazing feeding behaviour for both *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* which is consistent with their
32 specialised morphological adaptations for open habitats. In contrast, dental microwear suggests a
33 somewhat degree of plasticity in diets, as both species display microscopic features commonly
34 recorded in modern mixed feeders. ~~Similar results are also reported from other Late Pleistocene~~
35 ~~localities suggesting that these equids were able to shift their diet to a certain degree for limited~~
36 ~~periods of time.~~ Such a flexibility may be the reason for which they could have persisted even when
37 open grasslands were not the dominant landscape. Our findings provide a new line of evidence
38 supporting the idea that human activities (e.g., competition with the first domestic forms brought
39 from Eurasia and Africa) may have played a larger role in the extinction of some megafauna groups
40 than climate change per se.

41

42 **Highlights**

- 43 • Palaeoecology of Late Pleistocene equids from La Carihuela is investigated.
- 44 • Dental microwear patterns are consistent with a short-term mixed diet.
- 45 • Late Pleistocene equids could adapt to the reduction of open grasslands in Europe.
- 46 • Holocene climate warming may not have been the main trigger of their extinction.

47

48 **Keywords**

49 Palaeoenvironment; Equid Ecology; Dental mesowear; Dental microwear; Pleistocene; LGP

50

51 1. Introduction

52 The Late Quaternary Extinction (LQE) event led to the worldwide disappearance of several
53 megafaunal mammal species (Koch and Barnosky, 2006). Multiple explanations have been
54 proposed, suggesting that environmental changes at the end of the last Pleistocene glaciation,
55 human activity, or a combination of both, played a crucial role in this loss of biodiversity (Barnosky
56 et al. 2004; Koch and Barnosky, 2006; Faith and Surovell, 2009; Lyons et al., 2016). In the
57 European continent, this extinction event did ~~not~~ occur uniformly due to the presence of several
58 habitat refugia which allowed ~~to~~ some large mammals (e.g., woolly mammoths) to persist into the
59 Holocene in fragmented or isolated populations (~~Dale~~-Guthrie, 2004). Among these, wild horses
60 (*Equus ferus*) and the hydruntine or European wild ass (*Equus hydruntinus*) survived until the mid-
61 late Holocene when they disappear from both fossil and archeological records (Boulbes & van
62 Asperen, 2019). The decline and eventual disappearance of these last wild equids in Europe is
63 usually associated ~~to~~ with the reduction of steppe biomes due to the development of warmer
64 conditions after the Pleistocene/Holocene Transition, as well as to the arrival of domestic forms
65 brought by human populations from Western Eurasia and Africa (Kimura et al., 2010; Crees and
66 Turvey, 2014; Boulbes ~~&~~ and van Asperen, 2019; Librado et al., 2021).

67 According to palaeogenetic data (Bennett et al. 2017), *E. hydruntinus* became extinct in
68 Europe during the Bronze Age while the tempo and mode of the extinction of *E. ferus* is still
69 unclear with genetic data suggesting a substitution by domestic horses (*E. caballus*) which spread
70 from Western Eurasian steppes around 2200-2000 BC (Librado et al., 2021).

71 There are several hypotheses on the primary role of climate change or human activities
72 (hunting, domestication, overkill) or both on the extinction of the European megafauna during the
73 late Quaternary (Stuart, 2014). Due to morphological adaptations to live ~~n~~ in open grasslands and
74 grass eating (i.e., hypsodont dentition, cursorial locomotion), it is assumed that the raise in global
75 mean temperatures after the Last Glacial Maximum (with the subsequent reduction of dry and cold
76 grasslands) was the main trigger leading to the extinction of wild equids (Boulbes & van Asperen,

77 2019). Both *E. hydruntinus* and *E. ferus* are, however, consistently recorded (or even associated) in
78 several Middle and Late Pleistocene localities also during warm interglacial phases (Rivals et al.,
79 2009; Boulbes and van Asperen, 2019; Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2020; Mecozzi and Strani, 2021).
80 Understanding the palaeoecological adaptations of these equids and how they exploited available
81 plant resources emerges, therefore, as crucial to shed light on the role played by climatic and
82 environmental changes in their disappearance in Europe.

83 Dietary behaviour of fossil species can be inferred from different proxies; specifically
84 dental wear patterns provide data on the direct effects of ingested items (e.g., food, dust, grit)
85 produced over a long (mesowear) or short (microwear) period on tooth morphology (Fortelius and
86 Solounias, 2000; Solounias and Semprebon, 2002). Both dental meso- and microwear patterns are
87 thus strongly linked to feeding preferences and can provide information on fossil taxa² niche
88 occupation.

89 The Late Pleistocene Iberian locality of La Carihuela (Granada, Spain) yielded a rich
90 collection of *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* fossil material dated during the Last Glacial Period (LGP)
91 which is comprised of several dentognathic remains. By analysing dental wear patterns which
92 records two different timeframes, it is possible to investigate whether these equids exhibited a pure
93 grazing behaviour or, instead, ~~they~~ displayed a more flexible diet which may ~~had~~ have allowed
94 them to adapt even to less favorable landscapes due to climatic shifts.

95

96 **2. Material and Methods**

97

98 **2.1 Carihuela Cave**

99 Carihuela Cave is one of ~~the~~ several caves located 45 km northeast of Granada (Andalusia,
100 southern Spain) in the Píñar river valley (Fig. X1). The cave is comprised of six chambers which
101 have been excavated since the 1950s² (Spahni, 1955) unearthing a rich Late Pleistocene and

102 Holocene archaeo-palaeontological collection consisting of lithic artifacts and fossil vertebrates
103 (also recording human remains belonging to both Neanderthals and anatomically modern *Homo*)
104 (García-Sánchez, 1960; Vega-Toscano et al., 1988). The cave has been divided into twelve
105 Lithostratigraphic Units dated between 117 ± 41 ka and 1250 ± 60 years (Toscano et al., 1988;
106 Fernández et al., 2007 and references ~~therin~~therein) which have yielded several mammal remains,
107 among which those of wild horses and hydruntines are especially abundant (Fernández et al., 2007;
108 Samper Carro, 2010; Nacarino-Meneses et al., 2017).

109 No information is available about the exact stratigraphic position of the equid fossil material
110 examined in the present study, however, Fernández et al. (2007) and Samper Carro (2010) report
111 that the material of *E. ferus* (= *E. caballus* cf. *germanicus* in Fernández et al. [2007]) and *E.*
112 *hydruntinus* (Samper Carro, 2010) has been collected from Units X–VI, dated using
113 thermoluminescence approaches approximately between 70 and 37 ka (Vega-Toscano et al., 1988;
114 Fernández et al., 2007 and references therein) (Fig. 2). The material is currently stored at the
115 Museum of the Institut Català de Paleontologia Miquel Crusafont (ICP, Sabadell).

116

117 **2.2 Dental mesowear**

118 For herbivorous ungulates, dental mesowear is a direct signal of a species's diet representing
119 the cumulative effects of ingested items on the dental surface that are produced over a long period
120 of time compared to the lifespan of the animal (years or months; Fortelius and Solounias, 2000;
121 Strani et al., 2018a,b, 2019a). Attrition (tooth-to-tooth contact) and abrasion (tooth-to-food contact)
122 are the main factors that determine the tooth wear. High levels of attrition produce sharper cusps
123 and a higher dental occlusal relief, while high levels of abrasion lead to blunter cusps and low
124 occlusal relief. Modern ungulates which feed on soft plant resources (e.g., leaves, twigs, fruits,
125 buds) usually display higher levels of attrition while grazing animals ~~which~~whose diet is comprised
126 mostly of grasses, show a higher degree of abrasion due to abrasive silica contents present in
127 monocotyledonous plants (phytoliths) (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000). The effects of other particles

128 ingested while feeding at ground level (e.g., dust or grit) may also influence the tooth wear (Kaiser
129 et al., 2009) although it has been observed that some ruminants are capable ~~to~~ of "washing away"
130 exogenous particles in the rumen and then chewing ing on a "clean" bolus (Ackermans et al., 2018).

131 In this study, the traditional mesowear analysis originally limited to upper second molars
132 (M2) described by Fortelius and Solounias (2000) was extended to the whole upper molar row (M1-
133 M3) and to the upper fourth premolar (P4) following Kaiser and Solounias (2003) and DeMiguel et
134 al. (2012). Occlusal relief (high or low) and cusp shape (sharp, rounded, or blunt) of the apex of the
135 paracone or metacone were examined and converted to a single mesowear score (MWS) following
136 the "mesowear ruler" developed for scoring dental mesowear on fossil equids by Muhlbachler et al.
137 (2011). The method is based on seven cusp types (numbered from 0 to 6), ranging in shape from
138 high and sharp (stage 0) to completely blunt with no relief (stage 6). Additionally, a "stage 7" is
139 given to teeth with a convex cusp apex. ~~A total of~~ Of a total of 117 molars, 85 specimens were
140 scored using this method (*Equus ferus* N = 72; *Equus hydruntinus* N = 13). Teeth belonging to
141 either juvenile or old individuals were excluded from this analysis as mesowear is sensitive to the
142 ontogenic age of the animals (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000). Raw mesowear data are provided as
143 Supplementary Information (Table S1).

144

145 **2.3 Dental microwear**

146 Food and other material consumed during the last few days prior to the death of an animal,
147 leave microscopic patterns on ~~the teeth~~ tooth surfaces which are produced during the mastication
148 process, recording the so-called "last supper effect" (Grine, 1986; Strani et al., 2018c). These
149 microwear features were examined following the standard protocol developed by Solounias and
150 Semprebon (2002). Teeth were cleaned with acetone and alcohol, moulded with high-resolution
151 silicone (vinylpolysiloxane) and casts were created using clear epoxy resin. Casts were then
152 examined with a stereomicroscope equipped with a camera (Leica S9i) under incident light to reveal
153 microfeatures on the enamel. Specimens displaying badly preserved enamel, taphonomic distortions

154 or major post-mortem alterations (e.g., fresh features made during the collecting or storing process)
155 were excluded from the analysis following King et al. (1999) and Weber et al. (2021). Of a total of
156 117 molars, 42 specimens (*Equus ferus* N = 27; *Equus hydruntinus* N = 15) were suitable for this
157 analysis.

158 ~~A total of 42 specimens were examined (*Equus ferus* N = 27; *Equus hydruntinus* N = 15).~~
159 Upper molars (M1–M3) and fourth upper premolars (P4) were selected for this analysis as they are
160 the ones more involved in the mastication process. Second upper molars (M2) were preferably
161 selected. The anterior lingual blade of the paracone of upper cheek teeth and the posterior buccal
162 blade of the protoconid of lower molars was preferably sampled. If badly preserved, other facets
163 were selected. Following Solounias and Semprebon (2002), microwear features were observed at
164 35x magnification (Fig. 3), quantified in a standard square area of 0.16 mm² and divided into five
165 categories: small pits, large pits, fine scratches, coarse scratches, and gouges and also recording the
166 presence of cross scratches. The IC Measure software (ver. 2.0.0.286; The Imaging Source Europe
167 GmbH) was used to record microwear features.

168 Mean number of scratches and mean number of pits can be used to discriminate between
169 herbivorous ungulates with a browsing (i.e., animals feeding mostly on ligneous plant parts, bushes,
170 leaves, and fruits), grazing (i.e., animals feeding mostly on grasses), or mixed (i.e., animals feeding
171 on both food types) diet (Solounias and Semprebon, 2002; DeMiguel et al., 2008, 2011). The
172 percentage of individuals with scratch numbers falling in a low scratch range (%0–17) has also been
173 used to discriminate browsers, grazers, and mixed feeders (Semprebon and Rivals, 2007). In extant
174 ungulates, grazers have 0.0–22.2% of individuals with scratches between 0 and 17, mixed feeders
175 have 20.9–70.0% of individuals with scratches between 0 and 17, and leaf-dominated browsers
176 have 72.7–100.0% of individuals with scratches between 0 and 17 (Semprebon and Rivals, 2007).
177 Scratch textures were also converted into a Scratch Width Score (SWS) to simplify representation
178 of the data: ‘0’ to teeth with predominantly fine scratches per tooth surface, ‘1’ to those with a
179 mixture of fine and coarse types of textures, and ‘2’ to those with predominantly coarse scratches.

180 Individual scores for a sample were then averaged to get the SWS and compared to data of extant
181 taxa (data from Rivals, 2012 and references there-in). Raw microwear data are provided as
182 Supplementary Information (Table S2).

183

184 **2.4 Statistical analysis**

185 Discriminant analyses were performed to examine the resolution of both mesowear and
186 microwear variables applied to the fossil taxa. For the mesowear analysis, the percentages of high
187 relief, rounded and blunt cusps were used as independent variables and two dietary (conservative
188 and radical) classifications were used as grouping variables (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000). For
189 microwear, 1) average number of pits, 2) average number of scratches, 3) percentage of individuals
190 with predominantly fine scratches, 4) percentage of individuals with predominantly coarse
191 scratches, 5) percentage of individuals with a mixture of fine and coarse scratches, 6) percentage of
192 individuals with >4 large pits, 7) percentage of individuals with >4 cross scratches, and 8) the
193 percentage of individuals displaying gouges, were selected as independent variables and dietary
194 classifications of modern taxa (modified from Solounias and Semprebon [2002]) were used as
195 grouping variables. Analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 24.

196

197 **3. Results**

198

199 **3.1 Dental mesowear**

200 The *Equus ferus* mesowear pattern is characterised by a predominance of low occlusal relief
201 (79.2%) and rounded cusps (70.8%), though a few specimens display also sharp (19.4%) or blunt
202 ~~susps-cusps~~ (9.7%) (Table 1). *Equus hydruntinus* displays a similar pattern (%L = 69.2; %R = 69.2),
203 but contrary to that observed in *E. ferus*, none of the specimens exhibit blunt cusps and there is a
204 higher incidence of sharp cusps (30.8%) (Table 1). Both patterns result in a relatively high score

205 (MWS = 3.5 for *E. ferus* and 3.0 for *E. hydruntinus*) (Table 1) which points to a predominance of
206 abrasion over attrition in the wear process that is consistent with grazing diets. Few individuals
207 display a combination of low occlusal relief and sharp cusps (%L+S = 15.3 for *E. ferus* and 15.4 for
208 *E. hydruntinus*) (Table 1) a mesowear signal correlated with a diet based on grasses but also
209 including a component of open environment browse such as aridity-resistant shrubs (Fortelius and
210 Solounias, 2000). These results are in agreement with the discriminant analysis, which provides a
211 dietary discrimination of 74.1% of extant taxa correctly classified according to ~~the~~ both
212 classifications (68.5% and 74.1%, respectively, in cross-validation). Also, bivariate diagrams show
213 that both *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* are classified as grazers (Table 1; Fig. 4).

214

215 **3.2 Dental microwear**

216 Both *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* display a high number of scratches (*E. ferus* AS = 29.9; *E.*
217 *hydruntinus* AS = 25.9; Table 1), concordant with the consumption of a high amount of abrasive
218 items. The average numbers of scratches and pits are consistent with those observed in extant
219 ungulates with a diet characterized by a high intake of grasses (grazers and grass-dominated mixed
220 feeders) (Fig. 5). Only two specimens of each taxon show less than 17 scratches (*E. ferus* %0-17 =
221 3.7; *E. hydruntinus* %0-17 = 6.7; Table 1). Scratches are predominantly fine (*E. ferus* SWS = 0.1;
222 *E. hydruntinus* SWS = 0.2; Table 1) with similar lengths in both taxa (*E. hydruntinus* Average SL =
223 121.1 μm ; *E. ferus* Average SL = 126.9 μm ; Table S2). Coarse scratches are generally longer than
224 fine ones (Table S2) and *E. ferus* displays a higher percentage of cross scratches than *E.*
225 *hydruntinus* (%XS = 63 and 47 respectively; Table 1). Pits are generally small (*E. ferus* Average PS
226 = 59 μm ; *E. hydruntinus* Average PS = 64.3; Table S2) although a higher percentage of individuals
227 displaying large pits is recorded in *E. hydruntinus* if compared with *E. ferus* (%LP = 20 and 3.7
228 respectively; Table 1). Gouges are recorded in few individuals (*E. ferus* %G = 11.1; *E. hydruntinus*
229 %G = 13.3; Table 1).

230 While these microwear patterns point to a somewhat high abrasive diet, the marked
231 predominance of fine textured scratches is seldom observed in modern grazing ungulates which
232 instead display a predominance of coarser scratches especially in those species which feed mostly
233 on C4 grasses (Solounias and Semprebon, 2002). Abundant fine scratches are recorded in some
234 modern mixed feeders which feed on C3 grasses such as the Sumatran serow *Capricornis*
235 *sumatraensis*, the wapiti *Cervus canadensis*, the takin *Budorcas taxicolor* or in the llama *Lama*
236 *glama* who inhabits non-forested areas and feeds in alpine grasslands (Solounias and Semprebon,
237 2002).

238 Discriminant analysis performed using microwear variables classifies *E. ferus* and *E.*
239 *hydruntinus* as a seasonal and a meal-by-meal mixed feeder, respectively (72.2% correctly
240 classified modern taxa, 47.7% in cross-validation; Table 1; Fig. **MICRODISCR6**). When extant
241 seasonal and non-seasonal mixed feeders are grouped together in a single dietary category (named
242 as mixed feeder), both fossils are classified as mixed feeders (77.3% correctly classified modern
243 taxa, 61.4% in cross-validation; Table 1; Fig. 6). ~~This discrepancy between mesowear and
244 microwear results indicates that while both wild horses and hydruntines were well adapted to feed
245 on grasses, they could have displayed also a certain degree of flexibility in their dietary behaviour
246 when necessary, in order to consume less abrasive plant resources.~~

248 4. Discussion

249 4.1. Diet of *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from La Carihuela and comparison with species from 250 other Late Pleistocene sites from in Europe

251 Both *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from La Carihuela display a long-term grazing behaviour,
252 in agreement with that observed in *Equus* populations from other Late Pleistocene localities across
253 (Southern, Western and Central) Europe (from MIS 5 to MIS 2) (Rivals et al., 2009; Sánchez-
254 Hernández et al., 2020; Cirilli et al., 2022) (Table 2), and with their well-known (morphological)

255 adaptations (such as cursorial limbs, long metapodials, hypsodont cheek teeth, lophodont occlusal
256 patterns, etc.) for open habitats (MacFadden, 2005; Cirilli et al., 2022).

257 Regarding short-term feeding behaviours, apparently both equids were able to also exploit
258 plant resources other than grasses. While the high frequency of scratches and the low number of pits
259 are consistent with a diet characterized by high levels of abrasion, the predominance of finely
260 textured features are unusual for a strict grazing behaviour. Modern grazers (as well as bark eaters
261 and fruit browsers) tend in fact to display coarse scratches (Solounias and Semprebon, 2002), while
262 fine scratches are commonly observed in some extant ungulates displaying intermediate diets
263 (Solounias and Semprebon, 2002), such as the four-horned antelope *Tetracerus quadricornis*
264 (considered a grazer in Solounias and Semprebon, [2002], although dietary studies on living
265 populations by Kunwar et al., [2016] on living populations point to a mixed diet).

266 Interestingly, this finding is not recorded in *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from other Late
267 Pleistocene Iberian localities, which mostly display a SWS value above 0.5 (Rivals et al., 2009;
268 Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2020). A less abrasive short-term feeding behaviour in *E. ferus* is
269 recorded in other Late Pleistocene European localities, where microwear patterns points to a mixed
270 (at Portel-Ouest and Payre in France and Wallertheim in Germany during MIS 5e-d and MIS 4) or
271 even browsing (at Taubach and Salzgitter Lebenstedt in Germany during MIS 5e and MIS 3) diet
272 (Rivals et al., 2009) (Table 2). Individuals ascribed to *E. cf. ferus* from the another Iberian locality,
273 the Middle Pleistocene Vallparadís Estació layer EVT3, also display microwear patterns which are
274 consistent with a mixed feeding behaviour (Strani et al., 2019b), although this interpretation should
275 be tentatively taken as the sample consists of only two specimens. The available data for *E.*
276 *hydruntinus* from other European sites suggests that this equid usually displayed a grazing feeding
277 behaviour although microwear patterns consistent with a less abrasive diet are recorded at
278 Teixoneres Cave during the MIS 3 (Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2020Rivals et al., 2009).

279 This discrepancy between mesowear and microwear results indicates that while both wild
280 horses and hydruntines were well adapted to feed on grasses, they could have displayed also a

281 certain degree of flexibility in their dietary behaviour when necessary, in order to consume less
282 abrasive plant resources.

283 Finely textured scratches have been observed by Solounias and Semprebon (2002) in taxa
284 which feed on high altitude nicheshabitats where C3 grasses grow or that-which eat less abrasive
285 fresh or wet grasses. -La Carihuela cave is located at 1020 m above sea level (Fernández et al.,
286 2007) close to the Baetic System mountain ranges of Sierra Nevada, Sierra de Baza and Sierra de
287 María (Fig. 1). Thus, the abundance of fine scratches may ~~thus also be also~~ a result of the fact that
288 both equids feeding on C3 grasses in mountainous areas.

289 Among modern wild (or feral) equids, Przewalski horses (*Equus przewalskii*) and kulans
290 (*Equus hemionus kulan*) from Central Eurasia live in steppe-biomes in habitat and climatic
291 conditions that are comparable to those recorded in most European regions during the glacial phases
292 of the LGP. In Przewalski horses and kulan populations with overlapping home ranges, it has been
293 observed that time-differentiation of area usage allowed the two species to live in sympatric
294 conditions, with major overlapping (>60% of shared home range) occurring only during spring and
295 kulans showing higher mobility than Przewalski horses (Bahloul et al., 2001). Similar niche
296 partitioning mechanisms may had been employed by sympatric *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus*
297 populations at least during the most arid phases of the LGP, feeding on the same resources at
298 different times of the day and with *E. hydruntinus* exploiting a larger area compared to *E. ferus*.

300 ***4.2. The role of climatic changes and habitat alterations in the extinction of wild equids in*** 301 ***Europe***

302 The reduction of steppe-like biomes in Europe following the warming phase at the
303 beginning of the Holocene is considered the main factor that led to the extinction of *E. ferus* and *E.*
304 *hydruntinus* in the continent (Boulbes and van Asperen, 2019). Results from the La Carihuela
305 sample as well as from other European localities, however, indicate that despite the fact that wild
306 equids possessed marked adaptations for open grasslands feeding primarily on grazegrass, they

307 could adapt to feed also on other types of plant resources displaying a certain dietary flexibility
308 whether or not cold, dry, open habitats where the predominant element of the European landscapes.
309 *E. ferus* even displayed a short-term browsing behaviour during MIS 5e (Rivals et al., 2009), one of
310 the warmest interglacials of the Pleistocene characterized by global mean temperatures comparable
311 to projections for the current climate change, and wetter conditions than during the Holocene in
312 Central Europe (Rohling et al., 2007; Dabkowski and Limondin-Lozouet, 2021).

313 Pollen records for the Lithostratigraphic Units X–VI of La Carihuela which yielded *E. ferus*
314 and *E. hydruntinus* fossil remains, points to an alternation between pine forests (*Pinus*-dominated
315 open or closed woodland) and grasslands (Fernández et al., 2007) (Fig. 2). The absence of oaks
316 (*Quercus*) and deciduous trees across Units X–VI indicate generally cold climatic settings although
317 the record of mesothermophytes in Unit VI suggests warmer conditions around 40 ka (Fernández et
318 al., 2007). The lack of information on the exact stratigraphic provenance of the examined sample
319 does ~~not~~ allow us to correlate the studied material with a specific vegetation phase, however it
320 appears that *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from La Carihuela could successfully feed on the same
321 resources and avoid competitive displacement despite these repeated fluctuations between forest-
322 and grassland-dominated landscapes. It is possible that the recorded mixed feeding short-term diet
323 recorded is due to the sample consisting of animal specimens that may come from different Units
324 and thus lived under different climatic conditions.
325 Nevertheless, obtained results ~~This~~ suggest that Late Pleistocene wild equids could in fact adapt to
326 warmer and more humid conditions, and that while environmental changes certainly affected their
327 distribution "setting the stage" for their eventual extinction (e.g., locking them in habitat refugia
328 such as the Iberian Peninsula; Schmitt and Varga, {2012}), probably the arrival of and competition
329 with domestic forms and other livestock, may ~~had~~ have actually triggered and led to the
330 disappearance of wild equids in Europe as observed between modern Przewalski's horses and free-
331 ranging domestic ungulates (Sietses et al., 2009).

332

333 **5. Conclusions**

334 The role that major climatic changes and human activity played in the extinction of the last
335 European wild equids during the Pleistocene/Holocene Transition is not well understood. We report
336 for the first time a dietary reconstruction of *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from the Late Pleistocene
337 locality of La Carihuela (Iberian Peninsula), providing information on the niche partitioning that
338 these equids exhibited in southern Europe during the LGP. Dental mesowear and microwear
339 indicate that both wild horses and hydruntines occupied the same niche sharing similar long- and
340 short-term adaptations as grazers that could periodically shift their diet to also include less abrasive
341 plant resources. This, albeit limited in time, dietary flexibility is also recorded in other Late
342 Pleistocene European localities suggesting that both wild equids were capable ~~to adapt~~of adapting
343 to the reduction of steppe-like biomes. Holocene climatic changes may thus have not been the main
344 trigger of their disappearance. Human activity, specifically the spreading of domestic horses and
345 donkeys from Eurasia may have played a larger role in the extinction of wild equids in the continent
346 who may have been forced to compete with them for the same resources. We also highlight the
347 importance of a comprehensive microwear analysis when reconstructing the diet of fossil ungulates
348 including both quantitative (number of features) and qualitative (feature's texture) information to
349 discriminate between feeding behaviours.

350

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558 **Figure Captions**

559 **Figure 1.** La Carihuela geographical location (approximate coordinates: 37°26’56” N, 3°25’47”

560 W). Map generated from contours.axismaps.com. Contour interval: 500m.

561 **Figure 2.** Chronostratigraphy and lithostratigraphy of La Carihuela with correlated vegetation
562 information (modified from Fernández et al. 2007). Highlighted: units where *Equus ferus* and
563 *Equus hydruntinus* fossil remains have been recovered (from Fernández et al. 2007 and Samper
564 Carro, 2010). Abbreviations: Lithostratigraphic Units (LU), Pollen Zones (PZ). Silhouette image of
565 *E. ferus* by Flavia Strani, silhouette image of *E. hydruntinus* from PhyloPic.org (Public Domain).

566 **Figure 3.** Photomicrographs of enamel surfaces at 35× magnification of selected teeth. *Equus*
567 *ferus*: (A), specimen 54, left M1/M2 ~~sx~~; (B), specimen 77, right P4-~~dx~~; and (C), specimen 59, right
568 M1/M2-~~dx~~. *Equus hydruntinus*: (D), specimen 10b, right M2-~~dx~~; (E), specimen 11b, left M1/M2-~~sx~~;
569 and (F), specimen 7b, left M1/M2-~~sx~~. Scale bars: 500 µm.

570 **Figure 4.** Bivariate diagrams based on discriminant analysis performed with mesowear data: (A),
571 conservative classification; (B), radical classification. Group centroids: browsers (0); mixed feeders
572 (1); and grazers (2). Extant ungulates data from Fortelius and Solounias (2000).

573 **Figure 5.** Bivariate plot of the average number of pits versus average number of scratches in extant
574 ungulates (data modified from Solounias and Semprebon, 2002) and fossil equids from La
575 Carihuela. Silhouette image of *E. ferus* by Flavia Strani, silhouette image of *E. hydruntinus* from
576 PhyloPic.org (Public Domain).

577 **Figure 6.** Bivariate diagrams based on discriminant analysis performed with microwear data. (A),
578 classification using extant ungulates dietary types as grouping variables: fruit browsers (0); leaf
579 browsers (1); seasonal mixed feeders (2); meal-by-meal mixed feeders (3); and grazers (4). (B),
580 classification grouping extant seasonal and non-seasonal mixed feeders in a single dietary category
581 (mixed feeders): fruit browsers (0); leaf browsers (1); mixed feeders (2); and grazers (3). Square
582 symbol indicates group centroids. Extant ungulates data from Solounias and Semprebon (2002).

583

584 **Tables Captions**

585 **Table 1.** Summary of dental mesowear and microwear analysis.

586 Abbreviations (mesowear): number of specimens measured (N); percentage of specimens with high
587 (%High) and low (%Low) occlusal relief; percentage of specimens with sharp (%Sharp), rounded
588 (%Rounded) and blunt (%Blunt) cusps; percentage of individuals with low occlusal relief and sharp
589 cusps (%L+S); mesowear score (MWS); standar deviation (SD); coefficient of variation (CV).
590 Predicted diets according to a conservative (CONS) and radical (RAD) mesowear classification.

591 Abbreviations (microwear): average number of pits (AP); average number of scratches (AS);
592 percentage of individuals with more than 4 large pits (%Lp); percentage of individuals with gouges
593 (%G); percentage of individuals with more than 4 cross scratches (%XS); scratches width score
594 (SWS); percentage of specimens with between 0 and 17 scratches (%0-17); percentage of
595 individuals with predominantly fine scratches (%FS); percentage of individuals with a mix of fine
596 and coarse scratches (%MS); percentage of individuals with predominantly coarse scratches (%CS).

597 **Table 2.** Summary table of dietary adaptations of *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from selected Late
598 Pleistocene European localities.

599

600 **Supplementary Information**

601 **Table S1.** Raw mesowear data. Abbreviations: occlusal relief (OR); cusp shape (CS); mesowear
602 score (MWS); high (H) and low (L) occlusal relief; low occlusal relief (L); sharp (S), round (R) and
603 blunt (B) cusp; combination of low occlusal relief and sharp cusp (L+S).

604 **Table S2.** Raw microwear data. Abbreviations: small pits (SP); large pits (LP); total number of pits
605 (P); fine scratches (FS); coarse scratches (CS); total number of scratches (NS); cross scratches (XS).

606 Length and size are in μm and μm^2 respectively.

Response to Reviewers (ms ref. PALAEO-D-23-00188)

Reviewer #1: Wonderful study!!

1. The study is designed to elucidate the extent to which human activities, or the major climatic changes of the Pleistocene/Holocene Transition played a role in the extinction of the last European wild equids —*Equus ferus* and *Equus hydruntinus*.
2. The techniques used to investigate their patterns of dental wear, and therefore, their paleoecology—stereoscopic microwear and mesowear - are excellent proxies to elucidate paleodiet and paleohabitat as they have been shown to accurately discern both the abrasion encountered in the diet (i.e., mesowear) and the likely food items actually consumed by these fossil equids (microwear). Thus, the authors have chosen excellent proxies for answering the questions they had formulated in this study.
3. The Abstract is well done and reflects the content of the manuscript well, but it is a little long and could be strengthened by removing certain sentences that are not essential for the reader to gain a good understanding of the main points of the study. The content in these sentences are explored elsewhere in the manuscript so they can be removed. I suggest removing the following sentences: "A rich collection of *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* fossil material has been unearthed from the Late Pleistocene cave of La Carihuela (Granada, Iberian Peninsula), making this locality an optimal laboratory to investigate their palaeoecology." And "Similar results are also reported from other Late Pleistocene localities suggesting that these equids were able to shift their diet to a certain degree for limited periods of time."

Authors:

We are really grateful to the reviewer for the positive comments on how we designed this study. We edited the abstract following the reviewer suggestions, removing the sentences on the collection of La Carihuela cave and on the comparison with other Late Pleistocene localities.

Reviewer #1:

4. The Introduction is good - sticks to the questions of the study at hand and succinctly and clearly gives the reader enough background to understand what is known about the two fossil horses and ideas about the Late Quaternary Extinction, ideas on the extinction of megafauna at this time and the different temporal resolutions of the dental wear techniques employed in the study.
5. The Materials and Methods section is detailed enough to give the reader a good idea about the fossil locality where the fossil horses were excavated (Carihuela Cave) and the dental wear techniques used and statistical analytical tools used.
6. Results are clear-cut and reasonable considering that the authors were very thorough in their statistical analysis and used appropriate statistics for what they were testing.
7. Figures are excellent and easy to follow and the tables are fine. All tables and figures are necessary.
8. The Discussion is excellent but what has intrigued me is that both fossil horses have finely-textured scratches which is unusual in mostly grazing forms. Do the authors have any ideas as to what may have caused these finely-textured scratches? A sentence or two should be added to explore the possibilities. Solounias and Semprebon, 2002 noted finely textured scratches in taxa feeding on C3 grasses, occupying high altitude niches, or eating less abrasive, often fresh or wet grasses.

Authors:

We thank the reviewer for the useful suggestion on how to improve the Discussion section. We have added a new short paragraph (below) discussing the hypothesis of the abundance of fine scratches being a result of both equids feeding in high elevation areas.

“Finely textured scratches have been observed by Solounias and Semprebon (2002) in taxa which feed in high altitude niches where C3 grasses grow or that eat less abrasive fresh or wet grasses. La Carihuela cave is located at 1020 m above sea level (Fernández et al. 2007) close to the Baetic System mountain ranges of Sierra Nevada, Sierra de Baza and Sierra de María (Fig. 1). The abundance of fine scratches may thus also be a result of both equids feeding on C3 grasses in mountainous areas.”

Reviewer #1:

9. The Conclusions section is spot on.

Conclusions:

This is an excellent study and very well done. It should be published with very minor revision (please see my edits on uploaded manuscript). It is an important topic and the results are important to our understanding of the relative contributions of human activities vs. the major climatic changes of the Pleistocene/Holocene Transition in the extinction of the last European wild equids —*Equus ferus* and *Equus hydruntinus*.

Authors:

We are glad that our work has been positively received. We revised the manuscript following the minor edits indicated by the reviewer.

Reviewer #2: Review PALAEO-D-23-00188

This paper examines the diet of two species of equids that co-existed in Europe during the Late Pleistocene in order to investigate the role of climate in their extinction. The paper is well written and the methods applied according to the standard in low-magnification microwear analysis. The sample size is large enough to provide reliable results. The interpretations and conclusions are supported by the data. I only have some minor suggestions to improve the paper.

1. Mesowear is known to be sensitive to the ontogenic age of the individuals. In the method section about mesowear it would be useful to explain that the youngest individuals with unworn or slightly worn teeth and the old adults with heavy wear have been excluded from the analysis.

Authors:

The following sentence clarifying that teeth belonging to either juvenile or old individuals were excluded from the mesowear analysis has been added into the text:

“Teeth belonging to either juvenile or old individuals were excluded from this analysis as mesowear is sensitive to the ontogenic age of the animals (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000).”

Reviewer #2:

2. In the microwear section, the authors explained that teeth were carefully screened to remove

those showing string taphonomic alteration. I also suggest the authors to refer to the following papers recently published about tumbling and trampling respectively:

Uzunidis, A., Pineda, A., Jiménez-Manchón, S., Xafis, A., Ollivier, V., Rivals, F., 2021. The impact of sediment abrasion on tooth microwear analysis: an experimental study. *Archaeol Anthropol Sci* 13, 134. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-021-01382-5>

Micó, C., Blasco, R., Muñoz Del Pozo, A., Jiménez-García, B., Rosell, J., Rivals, F., 2023. Differentiating taphonomic features from trampling and dietary microwear, an experimental approach. *Historical Biology*, DOI: 10.1080/08912963.2023.2184690

Authors:

We thank the reviewer for the suggestion, but we prefer to cite the original paper, King et al. (1999), that describes the effect of a wide range of taphonomic alterations on the enamel surface and the Weber et al. (2021) work which provide a visual guide on post-mortem wear patterns in vertebrate teeth. We specifically used these papers to help us differentiate between diet-related microwear patterns and alteration features.

Reviewer #2:

3. At the beginning of the results section, it would be useful to state how many teeth were sampled in total, and how many were discarded from the microwear and mesowear analyses due to taphonomic reasons.

Authors:

We specified in the Material and Methods section the total number of molars that were available for the study (N = 117) and those that were selected for each analysis (N = 85 for the mesowear analysis and N = 42 for the microwear one).

Reviewer #2:

4. The last sentence of the results section (lines 237-240) is an interpretation of the results, the sentence should be integrated in the discussion.

Authors:

The sentence has been moved in the Discussion section (lines 279-282).

Reviewer #2:

5. Is the comparison with the two specimens from Vallparadis really needed here? In my opinion it does not bring any relevant information to the discussion. It is only a small sample (N=2) from an earlier chronology. If the authors want to compare with Middle Pleistocene horses they should include other published data. Here, I suggest to remove the sentence.

Authors:

We agree that the Vallparadis Estació sample size is small, and that result interpretation should be tentatively taken (we even stress this in the text; lines 274-275), however we believe that it is useful to mention those results as an indication that mixed feeders microwear patterns have been recorded in specimens ascribed to *Equus ferus* from the Iberian Peninsula also during the Middle Pleistocene. This has been now clarified in the text.

Reviewer #2:

6. The mixed feeding signal recorded by microwear could be due to time averaging in the archaeological units. As the sample results in the combination of teeth from 5 different units spanning a 33 ky period, the animals might have lived in different climatic conditions, or been hunted at different seasons in the various levels. This aspect could be discussed in section 4.2.

Authors:

Following the reviewer comments on the possibility that teeth may belong to animals that come from different layers of La Carihuela cave, we incorporated the following sentence in Section 4.2 (lines 322-324):

“It is possible that the recorded mixed feeding short-term diet is due to the sample consisting of animals that may come from different Units and thus lived in different climatic conditions.”

Reviewer #2:

7. On figure 5, it would be useful to see the error bars (SD or standard error of the mean, for example) to appreciate the interindividual variability (as well as to include SD/SEM values in Table 1). It would be also helpful to see the samples from Table 2 plotted on Figure 5 to appreciate the intraspecific diversity in diets. Two datasets and references could be added as comparative samples for NE Spain (*E. ferus*) and Crimea (mainly *E. hydruntinus*):

Ramírez-Pedraza, I., Rivals, F., Uthmeier, T., Chabai, V., 2020. Palaeoenvironmental and seasonal context of the Late Middle and Early Upper Palaeolithic occupations in Crimea: an approach using dental wear patterns in ungulates. *Archaeol. Anthropol. Sci.* 12, 268. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-020-01217-9>

Rivals, F., Uzunidis, A., Sanz, M., Daura, J., 2017. Faunal dietary response to the Heinrich Event 4 in southwestern Europe. *Palaeogeogr. Palaeoclimatol. Palaeoecol.* 473, 123-130. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2017.02.033>

Authors:

We thank the reviewer for the useful suggestions. Given that we focused mostly on the discussion of the results from La Carihuela locality we prefer to not include in Figure 5 the (many) samples from other European localities. Nevertheless, we have included SD and CV values for mesowear and microwear results in Table 1 as well as the datasets suggested by the reviewer in Table 2 which we thank for the indication.

Reviewer #2:

8. Other small minor corrections and comments:

- Line 21: To make clear that the authors refers to morphology, the word 'morphological' could be added before adaptations.
- Line 58: Remove the first name 'Dale' in the reference Guthrie 2004.
- Line 60: A reference is needed at the end of the sentence.
- Line 72: Delete the 'n' in 'liven'.
- Line 98: Change Fig. X to Fig. 1.
- Line 152: Change 'where' to 'were'
- Line 161: It could be added at the end of the sentence: on pictures of the enamel surfaces.
- Line 165: Before the references by DeMiguel, it could be added Solounias and Semperebon 2002.

- Line 196: Correct the word 'cusps' (instead of susps).
- Line 233: Replace MICRODISCR with the number 6 (Fig. 6).
- Line 272: Replace the citation Rivals et al. 2009 with Sánchez-Hernández et al. 2020 (it is the one about Teixoneres cave).
- Figure 2 is not cited in the text.

List of references:

Italics are missing on latin names on lines 348, 349, 364, 419, 446

Line 423: Change abrasioneattrition to abrasion-attrition.

Lines 490-491: Correct the journal name to: pour l'étude du Quaternaire

Authors:

All these minor edits have been addressed and following the reviewer recommendation we added the Boulbes & van Asperen (2019) reference, a review on the biostratigraphy of European *Equus*, at the end of line 60 (current line 61).

Reviewer #2:

Caption for figure 3: What is the meaning of sx and dx? Is it L and R?

Authors:

We edited the caption of Figure 3 spelling “right” and “left”.

Highlights

- Palaeoecology of Late Pleistocene equids from La Carihuela is investigated.
- Dental microwear patterns are consistent with a short-term mixed diet.
- Late Pleistocene equids could adapt to the reduction of open grasslands in Europe.
- Holocene climate warming may not have been the main trigger of their extinction.

*from Fernández et al. (2007)

Figure 5

Taxon		N	Mesowear				
			%High	%Low	%Sharp	%Round	
<i>Equus ferus</i>	Mean	72	20.8	79.2	19.4	70.8	9.7
	SD						
	CV						
<i>Equus hydruntinus</i>	Mean	13	30.8	69.2	30.8	69.2	0.0
	SD						
	CV						

Taxon		N	AP	AS	%LP	%G	Micro
							%XS
<i>Equus ferus</i>	Mean	27	12.9	29.9	3.7	11.1	63.0
	SD		5.8	7.3			
	CV		0.5	0.2			
<i>Equus hydruntinus</i>	Mean	15	17.5	25.9	20.0	13.3	46.7
	SD		8.6	7.1			
	CV		0.5	0.3			

*extant seasonal and non-seasonal mixed feeders are grouped together in a single dietary category "m"

%L+S	MWS	Predicted Diet	
		CONS	RAD
15.3	3.5	Grazer	Grazer
	1.5		
	0.4		
15.4	3.0	Grazer	Grazer
	1.6		
	0.5		

wear	%0-17	SWS	Predicted Diet			Type	Type*
			%FS (0 SWS)	%MS (1 SW)	%CS (2 SWS)		
	3.7	0.1	92.6	7.4	0.0	Seasonal Mixed Feeder	Mixed Feeder
	6.7	0.2	80.0	20.0	0.0	Meal-by-Meal Mixed Feeder	Mixed Feeder

ixed feeders"

MIS	Age	Taxa	Locality	Country
	Ma			
MIS2	0.022	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Gough's Cave	UK
MIS3	0.04	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Kent's Cavern	UK
MIS 4-3	0.07-0.037	<i>Equus ferus</i>	La Carihuela	Spain
MIS 4-3	0.07-0.037	<i>Equus hydruntinus</i>	La Carihuela	Spain
MIS 3	ca 0.035	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Canyars	Spain
MIS 3	0.045-	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Arbreda I	Spain
MIS 3	0.051-	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Teixoneres Cave IIIa	Spain
MIS 3	0.051-	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Teixoneres Cave IIIb	Spain
MIS 3	0.051-	<i>Equus hydruntinus</i>	Teixoneres Cave IIIa	Spain
MIS 3	0.051-	<i>Equus hydruntinus</i>	Teixoneres Cave IIIb	Spain
MIS 3	0.058-	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Salzgitter Lebenstedt	Germany
MIS 3	ca 0.05	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Abric Romanı KLM	Spain
MIS3	0.04	<i>Equus hydruntinus</i>	Emine Bair Khosar Cave	Ukraine
MIS2-4	0.062	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Aufhausener höhle	Germany
MIS 4		<i>Equus ferus</i>	Portel-Ouest F	France
MIS 5d-3	0.080-	<i>Equus hydruntinus</i>	Kabazi II	Ukraine
late MIS5	0.096	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Villa Seckendorff	Germany
late MIS5	0.096	<i>Equus hydruntinus</i>	Villa Seckendorff	Germany
MIS 5d		<i>Equus ferus</i>	Wallertheim F	Germany
MIS 5e		<i>Equus ferus</i>	Payre D	France
MIS 5e	0.116	<i>Equus ferus</i>	Taubach	Germany

Mesowear	Reference	Diet	Microwear
grazer	Saarinen et al. (2016)		grazer
grazer	Saarinen et al. (2016)		grazer
grazer	this study		mixed feeder
grazer	this study		mixed feeder
grazer	Rivals et al. (2017)		grazer
grazer	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)		grazer
grazer	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)		grazer
grazer	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)		grazer
grazer	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)		grazer
grazer	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)		mixed feeder
grass dom-mixed feeder	Rivals et al. (2009)		browser
grazer	Rivals et al. (2009)		grazer
grazer	Cirilli et al. (2022)		
grazer	Saarinen et al. (2016)		
grazer	Rivals et al. (2009)		mixed feeder
grazer	Ramírez-Pedraza et al. (2020)		grazer
grazer	Saarinen et al. (2016)		
grazer	Cirilli et al. (2022)		
grass dom-mixed feeder	Rivals et al. (2009)		grass dom-mixed feeder
grazer	Rivals et al. (2009)		mixed feeder
grazer	Saarinen et al. (2016)		browser

SWS	Reference
	Rivals and Lister (2016)
	Rivals and Lister (2016)
0.1	this study
0.2	this study
0.92	Rivals et al. (2017)
0.5	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)
0.55	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)
0.55	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)
0.63	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)
0.64	Sánchez-Hernández et al. (2020)
1.1	Rivals et al. (2009)
1.1-2.0-0.0	Rivals et al. (2009)
1.1	Rivals et al. (2009)
1.2	Ramírez-Pedraza et al. (2020)
0.5	Rivals et al. (2009)
1.1	Rivals et al. (2009)
1	Rivals et al. (2009)

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Flavia Strani reports financial support was provided by Italian Paleontological Society. The corresponding author (FS) and co-author (DDM) previously served as Reviewers for Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology

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Supplementary Material
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Supplementary Material
SI_Microwear CAR_REV1.xlsx

1 **The role of climate change in the extinction of the last wild equids of Europe: palaeoecology of**
2 ***Equus ferus* and *Equus hydruntinus* during the Last Glacial Period**

3
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13

14 **Abstract**

15 The last European wild equids —*Equus ferus* and *Equus hydruntinus*— were among the large
16 mammals (or megafauna) that became extinct during the Late Quaternary Extinction Event
17 disappearing from Europe during the Holocene. The role that the combined action of the major
18 climatic changes of the Pleistocene/Holocene Transition and the human activities played in their
19 extinction is not fully understood. The reduction of steppe-like biomes in Europe following the
20 increase of mean global temperatures during the Holocene is usually regarded as the main event that
21 triggered their disappearance, as both equids display typical morphological adaptations for open
22 grasslands and grass eating. However, *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* are found, often even co-occurring,
23 in both warm and cold phases of the Late Pleistocene. Thus, the investigation of their niche occupation
24 can help decipher whether their ecology and specialised dietary adaptations were the main reason of
25 their decline following the early Holocene global warming. Here we investigate the feeding strategies
26 of the two equids by studying their long- and short-term dietary adaptations through examination of

27 their patterns of dental wear. As expected, dental mesowear points to a highly abrasive diet
28 concordant with a grazing feeding behaviour for both *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* which is consistent
29 with their specialised morphological adaptations for open habitats. In contrast, dental microwear
30 suggests a somewhat degree of plasticity in diets, as both species display microscopic features
31 commonly recorded in modern mixed feeders. Such a flexibility may be the reason for which they
32 could have persisted even when open grasslands were not the dominant landscape. Our findings
33 provide a new line of evidence supporting the idea that human activities (e.g., competition with the
34 first domestic forms brought from Eurasia and Africa) may have played a larger role in the extinction
35 of some megafauna groups than climate change per se.

36

37 **Highlights**

- 38 • Palaeoecology of Late Pleistocene equids from La Carihuela is investigated.
- 39 • Dental microwear patterns are consistent with a short-term mixed diet.
- 40 • Late Pleistocene equids could adapt to the reduction of open grasslands in Europe.
- 41 • Holocene climate warming may not have been the main trigger of their extinction.

42

43 **Keywords**

44 Palaeoenvironment; Equid Ecology; Dental mesowear; Dental microwear; Pleistocene; LGP

45

46 **1. Introduction**

47 The Late Quaternary Extinction (LQE) event led to the worldwide disappearance of several
48 megafaunal mammal species (Koch and Barnosky, 2006). Multiple explanations have been proposed,
49 suggesting that environmental changes at the end of the last Pleistocene glaciation, human activity,
50 or a combination of both, played a crucial role in this loss of biodiversity (Barnosky et al. 2004; Koch
51 and Barnosky, 2006; Faith and Surovell, 2009; Lyons et al., 2016). In the European continent, this

52 extinction event did not occur uniformly due to the presence of several habitat refugia which allowed
53 some large mammals (e.g., woolly mammoths) to persist into the Holocene in fragmented or isolated
54 populations (Guthrie, 2004). Among these, wild horses (*Equus ferus*) and the hydruntine or European
55 wild ass (*Equus hydruntinus*) survived until the mid-late Holocene when they disappear from both
56 fossil and archeological records (Boulbes & van Asperen, 2019). The decline and eventual
57 disappearance of these last wild equids in Europe is usually associated with the reduction of steppe
58 biomes due to the development of warmer conditions after the Pleistocene/Holocene Transition, as
59 well as to the arrival of domestic forms brought by human populations from Western Eurasia and
60 Africa (Kimura et al., 2010; Crees and Turvey, 2014; Boulbes and van Asperen, 2019; Librado et al.,
61 2021).

62 According to palaeogenetic data (Bennett et al. 2017), *E. hydruntinus* became extinct in
63 Europe during the Bronze Age while the tempo and mode of the extinction of *E. ferus* is still unclear
64 with genetic data suggesting a substitution by domestic horses (*E. caballus*) which spread from
65 Western Eurasian steppes around 2200-2000 BC (Librado et al., 2021).

66 There are several hypotheses on the primary role of climate change or human activities
67 (hunting, domestication, overkill) or both on the extinction of the European megafauna during the
68 late Quaternary (Stuart, 2014). Due to morphological adaptations to live in open grasslands and grass
69 eating (i.e., hypsodont dentition, cursorial locomotion), it is assumed that the raise in global mean
70 temperatures after the Last Glacial Maximum (with the subsequent reduction of dry and cold
71 grasslands) was the main trigger leading to the extinction of wild equids (Boulbes & van Asperen,
72 2019). Both *E. hydruntinus* and *E. ferus* are, however, consistently recorded (or even associated) in
73 several Middle and Late Pleistocene localities also during warm interglacial phases (Rivals et al.,
74 2009; Boulbes and van Asperen, 2019; Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2020; Mecozzi and Strani, 2021).
75 Understanding the palaeoecological adaptations of these equids and how they exploited available
76 plant resources emerges, therefore, as crucial to shed light on the role played by climatic and
77 environmental changes in their disappearance in Europe.

78 Dietary behaviour of fossil species can be inferred from different proxies; specifically dental
79 wear patterns provide data on the direct effects of ingested items (e.g., food, dust, grit) produced over
80 a long (mesowear) or short (microwear) period on tooth morphology (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000;
81 Solounias and Semprebon, 2002). Both dental meso- and microwear patterns are thus strongly linked
82 to feeding preferences and can provide information on fossil taxa niche occupation.

83 The Late Pleistocene Iberian locality of La Carihuela (Granada, Spain) yielded a rich
84 collection of *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* fossil material dated during the Last Glacial Period (LGP)
85 which is comprised of several dentognathic remains. By analysing dental wear patterns which records
86 two different timeframes, it is possible to investigate whether these equids exhibited a pure grazing
87 behaviour or, instead, displayed a more flexible diet which may have allowed them to adapt even to
88 less favorable landscapes due to climatic shifts.

89

90 **2. Material and Methods**

91

92 **2.1 Carihuela Cave**

93 Carihuela Cave is one of several caves located 45 km northeast of Granada (Andalusia,
94 southern Spain) in the Píñar river valley (Fig. 1). The cave is comprised of six chambers which have
95 been excavated since the 1950s' (Spahni, 1955) unearthing a rich Late Pleistocene and Holocene
96 archaeo-palaeontological collection consisting of lithic artifacts and fossil vertebrates (also recording
97 human remains belonging to both Neanderthals and anatomically modern *Homo*) (García-Sánchez,
98 1960; Vega-Toscano et al., 1988). The cave has been divided into twelve Lithostratigraphic Units
99 dated between 117 ± 41 ka and 1250 ± 60 years (Toscano et al., 1988; Fernández et al., 2007 and
100 references therein) which have yielded several mammal remains, among which those of wild horses
101 and hydruntines are especially abundant (Fernández et al., 2007; Samper Carro, 2010; Nacarino-
102 Meneses et al., 2017).

103 No information is available about the exact stratigraphic position of the equid fossil material
104 examined in the present study, however, Fernández et al. (2007) and Samper Carro (2010) report that
105 the material of *E. ferus* (= *E. caballus* cf. *germanicus* in Fernández et al. [2007]) and *E. hydruntinus*
106 (Samper Carro, 2010) has been collected from Units X–VI, dated using thermoluminescence
107 approaches approximately between 70 and 37 ka (Vega-Toscano et al., 1988; Fernández et al., 2007
108 and references therein) (Fig. 2). The material is currently stored at the Museum of the Institut Català
109 de Paleontologia Miquel Crusafont (ICP, Sabadell).

110

111 **2.2 Dental mesowear**

112 For herbivorous ungulates, dental mesowear is a direct signal of a species's diet representing
113 the cumulative effects of ingested items on the dental surface that are produced over a long period of
114 time compared to the lifespan of the animal (years or months; Fortelius and Solounias, 2000; Strani
115 et al., 2018a,b, 2019a). Attrition (tooth-to-tooth contact) and abrasion (tooth-to-food contact) are the
116 main factors that determine the tooth wear. High levels of attrition produce sharper cusps and a higher
117 dental occlusal relief, while high levels of abrasion lead to blunter cusps and low occlusal relief.
118 Modern ungulates which feed on soft plant resources (e.g., leaves, twigs, fruits, buds) usually display
119 higher levels of attrition while grazing animals whose diet is comprised mostly of grasses, show a
120 higher degree of abrasion due to abrasive silica contents present in monocotyledonous plants
121 (phytoliths) (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000). The effects of other particles ingested while feeding at
122 ground level (e.g., dust or grit) may also influence the tooth wear (Kaiser et al., 2009) although it has
123 been observed that some ruminants are capable of "washing away" exogenous particles in the rumen
124 and then chewing on a "clean" bolus (Ackermans et al., 2018).

125 In this study, the traditional mesowear analysis originally limited to upper second molars (M2)
126 described by Fortelius and Solounias (2000) was extended to the whole upper molar row (M1-M3)
127 and to the upper fourth premolar (P4) following Kaiser and Solounias (2003) and DeMiguel et al.
128 (2012). Occlusal relief (high or low) and cusp shape (sharp, rounded, or blunt) of the apex of the

129 paracone or metacone were examined and converted to a single mesowear score (MWS) following
130 the “mesowear ruler” developed for scoring dental mesowear on fossil equids by Mihlbachler et al.
131 (2011). The method is based on seven cusp types (numbered from 0 to 6), ranging in shape from high
132 and sharp (stage 0) to completely blunt with no relief (stage 6). Additionally, a "stage 7" is given to
133 teeth with a convex cusp apex. Of a total of 117 molars, 85 specimens were scored using this method
134 (*Equus ferus* N = 72; *Equus hydruntinus* N = 13). Teeth belonging to either juvenile or old individuals
135 were excluded from this analysis as mesowear is sensitive to the ontogenic age of the animals
136 (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000). Raw mesowear data are provided as Supplementary Information
137 (Table S1).

138

139 **2.3 Dental microwear**

140 Food and other material consumed during the last few days prior to the death of an animal,
141 leave microscopic patterns on tooth surfaces which are produced during the mastication process,
142 recording the so-called “last supper effect” (Grine, 1986; Strani et al., 2018c). These microwear
143 features were examined following the standard protocol developed by Solounias and Semprebon
144 (2002). Teeth were cleaned with acetone and alcohol, moulded with high-resolution silicone
145 (vinylpolysiloxane) and casts were created using clear epoxy resin. Casts were then examined with a
146 stereomicroscope equipped with a camera (Leica S9i) under incident light to reveal microfeatures on
147 the enamel. Specimens displaying badly preserved enamel, taphonomic distortions or major post-
148 mortem alterations (e.g., fresh features made during the collecting or storing process) were excluded
149 from the analysis following King et al. (1999) and Weber et al. (2021). Of a total of 117 molars, 42
150 specimens (*Equus ferus* N = 27; *Equus hydruntinus* N = 15) were suitable for this analysis.

151 Upper molars (M1–M3) and fourth upper premolars (P4) were selected for this analysis as
152 they are the ones more involved in the mastication process. Second upper molars (M2) were
153 preferably selected. The anterior lingual blade of the paracone of upper cheek teeth and the posterior
154 buccal blade of the protoconid of lower molars was preferably sampled. If badly preserved, other

155 facets were selected. Following Solounias and Semprebon (2002), microwear features were
156 observed at 35x magnification (Fig. 3), quantified in a standard square area of 0.16 mm² and divided
157 into five categories: small pits, large pits, fine scratches, coarse scratches, and gouges and also
158 recording the presence of cross scratches. The IC Measure software (ver. 2.0.0.286; The Imaging
159 Source Europe GmbH) was used to record microwear features.

160 Mean number of scratches and mean number of pits can be used to discriminate between
161 herbivorous ungulates with a browsing (i.e., animals feeding mostly on ligneous plant parts, bushes,
162 leaves, and fruits), grazing (i.e., animals feeding mostly on grasses), or mixed (i.e., animals feeding
163 on both food types) diet (Solounias and Semprebon, 2002; DeMiguel et al., 2008, 2011). The
164 percentage of individuals with scratch numbers falling in a low scratch range (0–17) has also been
165 used to discriminate browsers, grazers, and mixed feeders (Semprebon and Rivals, 2007). In extant
166 ungulates, grazers have 0.0–22.2% of individuals with scratches between 0 and 17, mixed feeders
167 have 20.9–70.0% of individuals with scratches between 0 and 17, and leaf-dominated browsers have
168 72.7–100.0% of individuals with scratches between 0 and 17 (Semprebon and Rivals, 2007). Scratch
169 textures were also converted into a Scratch Width Score (SWS) to simplify representation of the data:
170 ‘0’ to teeth with predominantly fine scratches per tooth surface, ‘1’ to those with a mixture of fine
171 and coarse types of textures, and ‘2’ to those with predominantly coarse scratches. Individual scores
172 for a sample were then averaged to get the SWS and compared to data of extant taxa (data from
173 Rivals, 2012 and references therein). Raw microwear data are provided as Supplementary
174 Information (Table S2).

175

176 ***2.4 Statistical analysis***

177 Discriminant analyses were performed to examine the resolution of both mesowear and
178 microwear variables applied to the fossil taxa. For the mesowear analysis, the percentages of high
179 relief, rounded and blunt cusps were used as independent variables and two dietary (conservative and
180 radical) classifications were used as grouping variables (Fortelius and Solounias, 2000). For

181 microwear, 1) average number of pits, 2) average number of scratches, 3) percentage of individuals
182 with predominantly fine scratches, 4) percentage of individuals with predominantly coarse scratches,
183 5) percentage of individuals with a mixture of fine and coarse scratches, 6) percentage of individuals
184 with >4 large pits, 7) percentage of individuals with >4 cross scratches, and 8) the percentage of
185 individuals displaying gouges, were selected as independent variables and dietary classifications of
186 modern taxa (modified from Solounias and Semprebon [2002]) were used as grouping variables.
187 Analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 24.

188

189 **3. Results**

190

191 **3.1 Dental mesowear**

192 The *Equus ferus* mesowear pattern is characterised by a predominance of low occlusal relief
193 (79.2%) and rounded cusps (70.8%), though a few specimens display also sharp (19.4%) or blunt
194 cusps (9.7%) (Table 1). *Equus hydruntinus* displays a similar pattern (%L = 69.2; %R = 69.2), but
195 contrary to that observed in *E. ferus*, none of the specimens exhibit blunt cusps and there is a higher
196 incidence of sharp cusps (30.8%) (Table 1). Both patterns result in a relatively high score (MWS =
197 3.5 for *E. ferus* and 3.0 for *E. hydruntinus*) (Table 1) which points to a predominance of abrasion over
198 attrition in the wear process that is consistent with grazing diets. Few individuals display a
199 combination of low occlusal relief and sharp cusps (%L+S = 15.3 for *E. ferus* and 15.4 for *E.*
200 *hydruntinus*) (Table 1) a mesowear signal correlated with a diet based on grasses but also including
201 a component of open environment browse such as aridity-resistant shrubs (Fortelius and Solounias,
202 2000). These results are in agreement with the discriminant analysis, which provides a dietary
203 discrimination of 74.1% of extant taxa correctly classified according to both classifications (68.5%
204 and 74.1%, respectively, in cross-validation). Also, bivariate diagrams show that both *E. ferus* and *E.*
205 *hydruntinus* are classified as grazers (Table 1; Fig. 4).

206

207 **3.2 Dental microwear**

208 Both *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* display a high number of scratches (*E. ferus* AS = 29.9; *E.*
209 *hydruntinus* AS = 25.9; Table 1), concordant with the consumption of a high amount of abrasive
210 items. The average numbers of scratches and pits are consistent with those observed in extant
211 ungulates with a diet characterized by a high intake of grasses (grazers and grass-dominated mixed
212 feeders) (Fig. 5). Only two specimens of each taxon show less than 17 scratches (*E. ferus* %0-17 =
213 3.7; *E. hydruntinus* %0-17 = 6.7; Table 1). Scratches are predominantly fine (*E. ferus* SWS = 0.1; *E.*
214 *hydruntinus* SWS = 0.2; Table 1) with similar lengths in both taxa (*E. hydruntinus* Average SL =
215 121.1 μm ; *E. ferus* Average SL = 126.9 μm ; Table S2). Coarse scratches are generally longer than
216 fine ones (Table S2) and *E. ferus* displays a higher percentage of cross scratches than *E. hydruntinus*
217 (%XS = 63 and 47 respectively; Table 1). Pits are generally small (*E. ferus* Average PS = 59 μm ; *E.*
218 *hydruntinus* Average PS = 64.3; Table S2) although a higher percentage of individuals displaying
219 large pits is recorded in *E. hydruntinus* if compared with *E. ferus* (%LP = 20 and 3.7 respectively;
220 Table 1). Gouges are recorded in few individuals (*E. ferus* %G = 11.1; *E. hydruntinus* %G = 13.3;
221 Table 1).

222 While these microwear patterns point to a somewhat high abrasive diet, the marked
223 predominance of fine textured scratches is seldom observed in modern grazing ungulates which
224 instead display a predominance of coarser scratches especially in those species which feed mostly on
225 C4 grasses (Solounias and Semprebon, 2002). Abundant fine scratches are recorded in some modern
226 mixed feeders which feed on C3 grasses such as the Sumatran serow *Capricornis sumatraensis*, the
227 wapiti *Cervus canadensis*, the takin *Budorcas taxicolor* or in the llama *Lama glama* who inhabits
228 non-forested areas and feeds in alpine grasslands (Solounias and Semprebon, 2002).

229 Discriminant analysis performed using microwear variables classifies *E. ferus* and *E.*
230 *hydruntinus* as a seasonal and a meal-by-meal mixed feeder, respectively (72.2% correctly classified
231 modern taxa, 47.7% in cross-validation; Table 1, Fig. 6). When extant seasonal and non-seasonal

232 mixed feeders are grouped together in a single dietary category (named as mixed feeder), both fossils
233 are classified as mixed feeders (77.3% correctly classified modern taxa, 61.4% in cross-validation;
234 Table 1, Fig. 6).

235

236 **4. Discussion**

237 ***4.1. Diet of E. ferus and E. hydruntinus from La Carihuela and comparison with species from*** 238 ***other Late Pleistocene sites in Europe***

239 Both *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from La Carihuela display a long-term grazing behaviour,
240 in agreement with that observed in *Equus* populations from other Late Pleistocene localities across
241 (Southern, Western and Central) Europe (from MIS 5 to MIS 2) (Rivals et al., 2009; Sánchez-
242 Hernández et al., 2020; Cirilli et al., 2022) (Table 2), and with their well-known (morphological)
243 adaptations (such as cursorial limbs, long metapodials, hypsodont cheek teeth, lophodont occlusal
244 patterns, etc.) for open habitats (MacFadden, 2005; Cirilli et al., 2022).

245 Regarding short-term feeding behaviour, apparently both equids were able to also exploit
246 plant resources other than grasses. While the high frequency of scratches and the low number of pits
247 are consistent with a diet characterized by high levels of abrasion, the predominance of finely textured
248 features are unusual for a strict grazing behaviour. Modern grazers (as well as bark eaters and fruit
249 browsers) tend in fact to display coarse scratches (Solounias and Semprebon, 2002), while fine
250 scratches are commonly observed in some extant ungulates displaying intermediate diets (Solounias
251 and Semprebon, 2002), such as the four-horned antelope *Tetracerus quadricornis* (considered a
252 grazer in Solounias and Semprebon, 2002, although dietary studies by Kunwar et al., 2016 on living
253 populations point to a mixed diet).

254 Interestingly, this finding is not recorded in *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from other Late
255 Pleistocene Iberian localities, which mostly display a SWS value above 0.5 (Rivals et al., 2009;
256 Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2020). A less abrasive short-term feeding behaviour in *E. ferus* is recorded
257 in other Late Pleistocene European localities, where microwear patterns points to a mixed (at Portel-

258 Ouest and Payre in France and Wallertheim in Germany during MIS 5e-d and MIS 4) or even
259 browsing (at Taubach and Salzgitter Lebenstedt in Germany during MIS 5e and MIS 3) diet (Rivals
260 et al., 2009) (Table 2). Individuals ascribed to *E. cf. ferus* from another Iberian locality, the Middle
261 Pleistocene Vallparadís Estació layer EVT3, also display microwear patterns which are consistent
262 with a mixed feeding behaviour (Strani et al., 2019b), although this interpretation should be tentatively
263 taken as the sample consists of only two specimens. The available data for *E. hydruntinus* from other
264 European sites suggests that this equid usually displayed a grazing feeding behaviour although
265 microwear patterns consistent with a less abrasive diet are recorded at Teixoneres Cave during the
266 MIS 3 (Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2020).

267 The discrepancy between mesowear and microwear results indicates that while both wild
268 horses and hydruntines were well adapted to feed on grasses, they could have displayed also a certain
269 degree of flexibility in their dietary behaviour when necessary, in order to consume less abrasive plant
270 resources.

271 Finely textured scratches have been observed by Solounias and Semprebon (2002) in taxa
272 which feed on high altitude habitats where C3 grasses grow or which eat less abrasive fresh or wet
273 grasses. La Carihuela cave is located at 1020 m above sea level (Fernández et al., 2007) close to the
274 Baetic System mountain ranges of Sierra Nevada, Sierra de Baza and Sierra de María (Fig. 1). Thus,
275 the abundance of fine scratches may be also a result of the fact that both equids fed on C3 grasses in
276 mountainous areas.

277 Among modern wild (or feral) equids, Przewalski horses (*Equus przewalskii*) and kulans
278 (*Equus hemionus kulan*) from Central Eurasia live in steppe-biomes in habitat and climatic conditions
279 that are comparable to those recorded in most European regions during the glacial phases of the LGP.
280 In Przewalski horses and kulan populations with overlapping home ranges, it has been observed that
281 time-differentiation of area usage allowed the two species to live in sympatric conditions, with major
282 overlapping (>60% of shared home range) occurring only during spring and kulans showing higher
283 mobility than Przewalski horses (Bahloul et al., 2001). Similar niche partitioning mechanisms may

284 had been employed by sympatric *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* populations at least during the most arid
285 phases of the LGP, feeding on the same resources at different times of the day and with *E. hydruntinus*
286 exploiting a larger area compared to *E. ferus*.

287

288 **4.2. The role of climatic changes and habitat alterations in the extinction of wild equids in Europe**

289 The reduction of steppe-like biomes in Europe following the warming phase at the beginning
290 of the Holocene is considered the main factor that led to the extinction of *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus*
291 in the continent (Boulbes and van Asperen, 2019). Results from the La Carihuela sample as well as
292 from other European localities, however, indicate that despite the fact that wild equids possessed
293 marked adaptations for open grasslands feeding primarily on grass, they could adapt to feed also on
294 other types of plant resources displaying a certain dietary flexibility whether or not cold, dry, open
295 habitats were the predominant element of the European landscapes. *E. ferus* even displayed a short-
296 term browsing behaviour during MIS 5e (Rivals et al., 2009), one of the warmest interglacials of the
297 Pleistocene characterized by global mean temperatures comparable to projections for the current
298 climate change, and wetter conditions than during the Holocene in Central Europe (Rohling et al.,
299 2007; Dabkowski and Limondin-Lozouet, 2021).

300 Pollen records for the Lithostratigraphic Units X–VI of La Carihuela which yielded *E. ferus*
301 and *E. hydruntinus* fossil remains, point to an alternation between pine forests (*Pinus*-dominated open
302 or closed woodland) and grasslands (Fernández et al., 2007) (Fig. 2). The absence of oaks (*Quercus*)
303 and deciduous trees across Units X–VI indicate generally cold climatic settings although the record
304 of mesothermophytes in Unit VI suggests warmer conditions around 40 ka (Fernández et al., 2007).
305 The lack of information on the exact stratigraphic provenance of the examined sample does not allow
306 us to correlate the studied material with a specific vegetation phase, however it appears that *E. ferus*
307 and *E. hydruntinus* from La Carihuela could successfully feed on the same resources and avoid
308 competitive displacement despite these repeated fluctuations between forest- and grassland-
309 dominated landscapes. It is possible that the mixed feeding short-term diet recorded is due to a sample

310 consisting of specimens that may come from different units and thus lived under different climatic
311 conditions.

312 Nevertheless, obtained results suggest that Late Pleistocene wild equids could in fact adapt to warmer
313 and more humid conditions, and that while environmental changes certainly affected their distribution
314 "setting the stage" for their eventual extinction (e.g., locking them in habitat refugia such as the
315 Iberian Peninsula; Schmitt and Varga, 2012), probably the arrival of and competition with domestic
316 forms and other livestock, may have actually triggered and led to the disappearance of wild equids in
317 Europe as observed between modern Przewalski's horses and free-ranging domestic ungulates
318 (Sietses et al., 2009).

319

320 **5. Conclusions**

321 The role that major climatic changes and human activity played in the extinction of the last
322 European wild equids during the Pleistocene/Holocene Transition is not well understood. We report
323 for the first time a dietary reconstruction of *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from the Late Pleistocene
324 locality of La Carihuela (Iberian Peninsula), providing information on the niche partitioning that these
325 equids exhibited in southern Europe during the LGP. Dental mesowear and microwear indicate that
326 both wild horses and hydruntines occupied the same niche sharing similar long- and short-term
327 adaptations as grazers that could periodically shift their diet to also include less abrasive plant
328 resources. This, albeit limited in time, dietary flexibility is also recorded in other Late Pleistocene
329 European localities suggesting that both wild equids were capable of adapting to the reduction of
330 steppe-like biomes. Holocene climatic changes may thus have not been the main trigger of their
331 disappearance. Human activity, specifically the spreading of domestic horses and donkeys from
332 Eurasia may have played a larger role in the extinction of wild equids in the continent who may have
333 been forced to compete with them for the same resources. We also highlight the importance of a
334 comprehensive microwear analysis when reconstructing the diet of fossil ungulates including both

335 quantitative (number of features) and qualitative (feature's texture) information to discriminate
336 between feeding behaviours.

337

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347

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541

542 **Figure Captions**

543 **Figure 1.** La Carihuela geographical location (approximate coordinates: 37°26'56" N, 3°25'47" W).
544 Map generated from contours.axismaps.com. Contour interval: 500m.

545 **Figure 2.** Chronostratigraphy and lithostratigraphy of La Carihuela with correlated vegetation
546 information (modified from Fernández et al. 2007). Highlighted: units where *Equus ferus* and *Equus*
547 *hydruntinus* fossil remains have been recovered (from Fernández et al. 2007 and Samper Carro,
548 2010). Abbreviations: Lithostratigraphic Units (LU), Pollen Zones (PZ). Silhouette image of *E. ferus*
549 by Flavia Strani, silhouette image of *E. hydruntinus* from PhyloPic.org (Public Domain).

550 **Figure 3.** Photomicrographs of enamel surfaces at 35× magnification of selected teeth. *Equus ferus*:
551 (A), specimen 54, left M1/M2 ; (B), specimen 77, right P4; and (C), specimen 59, right M1/M2.
552 *Equus hydruntinus*: (D), specimen 10b, right M2; (E), specimen 11b, left M1/M2; and (F), specimen
553 7b, left M1/M2. Scale bars: 500 µm.

554 **Figure 4.** Bivariate diagrams based on discriminant analysis performed with mesowear data: (A),
555 conservative classification; (B), radical classification. Group centroids: browsers (0); mixed feeders
556 (1); and grazers (2). Extant ungulates data from Fortelius and Solounias (2000).

557 **Figure 5.** Bivariate plot of the average number of pits versus average number of scratches in extant
558 ungulates (data modified from Solounias and Semprebon, 2002) and fossil equids from La Carihuela.
559 Silhouette image of *E. ferus* by Flavia Strani, silhouette image of *E. hydruntinus* from PhyloPic.org
560 (Public Domain).

561 **Figure 6.** Bivariate diagrams based on discriminant analysis performed with microwear data. (A),
562 classification using extant ungulates dietary types as grouping variables: fruit browsers (0); leaf
563 browsers (1); seasonal mixed feeders (2); meal-by-meal mixed feeders (3); and grazers (4). (B),

564 classification grouping extant seasonal and non-seasonal mixed feeders in a single dietary category
565 (mixed feeders): fruit browsers (0); leaf browsers (1); mixed feeders (2); and grazers (3). Square
566 symbol indicates group centroids. Extant ungulates data from Solounias and Semperebon (2002).

567

568 **Tables Captions**

569 **Table 1.** Summary of dental mesowear and microwear analysis.

570 Abbreviations (mesowear): number of specimens measured (N); percentage of specimens with high
571 (%High) and low (%Low) occlusal relief; percentage of specimens with sharp (%Sharp), rounded
572 (%Rounded) and blunt (%Blunt) cusps; percentage of individuals with low occlusal relief and sharp
573 cusps (%L+S); mesowear score (MWS); standar deviation (SD); coefficient of variation (CV).
574 Predicted diets according to a conservative (CONS) and radical (RAD) mesowear classification.

575 Abbreviations (microwear): average number of pits (AP); average number of scratches (AS);
576 percentage of individuals with more than 4 large pits (%Lp); percentage of individuals with gouges
577 (%G); percentage of individuals with more than 4 cross scratches (%XS); scratches width score
578 (SWS); percentage of specimens with between 0 and 17 scratches (%0-17); percentage of individuals
579 with predominantly fine scratches (%FS); percentage of individuals with a mix of fine and coarse
580 scratches (%MS); percentage of individuals with predominantly coarse scratches (%CS).

581 **Table 2.** Summary table of dietary adaptations of *E. ferus* and *E. hydruntinus* from selected Late
582 Pleistocene European localities.

583

584 **Supplementary Information**

585 **Table S1.** Raw mesowear data. Abbreviations: occlusal relief (OR); cusp shape (CS); mesowear score
586 (MWS); high (H) and low (L) occlusal relief; low occlusal relief (L); sharp (S), round (R) and blunt
587 (B) cusp; combination of low occlusal relief and sharp cusp (L+S).

588 **Table S2.** Raw microwear data. Abbreviations: small pits (SP); large pits (LP); total number of pits
589 (P); fine scratches (FS); coarse scratches (CS); total number of scratches (NS); cross scratches (XS).
590 Length and size are in μm and μm^2 respectively.